
A Study on the Impact of Kanyashree Prokalpa on Girl Students

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ABSTRACT

The present study investigates the impact of the Kanyashree Prakalpa on girl students, with special reference to the North 24 Parganas district of West Bengal. Launched in 2013 as a conditional cash transfer scheme, the programme aims to enhance girls' educational participation, delay early marriage, and promote socio-economic empowerment. The study adopts a survey-based qualitative research design, collecting data from 200 secondary-level girl students across five government higher secondary schools. The findings reveal a high level of awareness among beneficiaries regarding the scheme. It significantly contributes to reducing dropout rates, encouraging continuation of education, and delaying child marriage. Financial incentives under Kanyashree (K-1, K-2, and K-3) act as motivating factors for girls to pursue secondary and higher education. Moreover, the scheme fosters self-confidence, decision-making ability, and social empowerment among adolescent girls. Despite certain limitations, the study concludes that Kanyashree Prakalpa has brought measurable positive changes in educational attainment and social status of girls, making it an effective model for gender-sensitive policy intervention.

INTRODUCTION

Kanyashree Prakalpa is one of the public services initiated by the Government of West Bengal in the year 2013. The principle Objectives of Kanyashree Prakalpa are as Follows-

Kanyashree Prakalpa seeks to improve the status and wellbeing of girls, specifically those from socioeconomically disadvantaged families through conditional Cash Transfer by:

- (a) Incentivizing them to continue in education for a longer period of time, and complete secondary or higher secondary education or equivalent in technical or vocational streams, thereby giving them a better footing in both the economic and social spheres.
- (b) Disincentivising marriage till at least the age of 18, the legal age of marriage, thereby Reducing the risks of early pregnancies associated risks of maternal and child mortality, and other debilitating health conditions, including those of Malnutrition.
- (c) It was also decided that the scheme should confer more than just monetary support. It should be a means of financial inclusion and a tool of empowerment for adolescent girls. The schemes benefits are there for paid directly to Bank Accounts in the girl's names, leaving the decision of utilization of the money in their hands.
- (d) To reinforce the positive impact of increased education and delayed marriage, the scheme also works to enhance the social power and self-esteem of girls through a targeted behavior change communication strategy. The communication strategy not only builds awareness of the scheme, but includes adolescent-friendly approaches like events completions and Kanyashree clubs, and the endorsement of strong women figures as role models to promote social and psychological empowerment

As more and more girls remain in school, it is envisaged that they will use the opportunity to gain skills and knowledge that will help them become economically independent. Even If girls do get married soon after they turn 18. It is expected that their education and enhanced social and emotional development will give them a better foundation for in their adult lives. And over the time as entire generations of women enter marriages only after they have some degree of economic Independence, It is expected that the practice of child marriage is completely eradicated and women will attain their right to health, education and socioeconomic equality.

In June, 2017 this public services had received the international recognition United Nations honors Kanyashree with highest public service award. Kanyashree was ranked the best among 552 such social sector schemes from across 62 countries that were nominated for the coveted award.

Kanyashree Prakalpa is government sponsored schemes in West Bengal which will be implemented henceforth in all district of the state while a number of factors contribute to reduce girls dropping out of

school. Human Rights researches show that the major obstacles to girls' education are child marriage and domestic chores. Ensuring that girls stay in school is one of the most effective protective measures against child marriage given that child marriage has a grossly negative impact on the lives of children, adolescence and young women. This scheme is expected to bring about measurable improved outcomes for the education, health and empowerment of the girls, their children and immeasurable benefits for larger society. The purpose of this initiative is to uplift those girls who are from poor families and thus cannot pursue higher studies due to their economic conditions. It has been given international recognition by the United Kingdoms Department of International Development and the UNICEF. Educating girls helps to make communities and societies healthier, wealthier, and safer, and can also help to reduce child deaths, improve maternal health and tackle the spread of HIV and AIDS. Previously the society thought girls to be inferior to boys. They thought girls to be a liability so they gave premature marriage to the girls and did not bother to make them educated. Now this stereotype custom is sought to be broken. The society is slowly feeling the need of educating them.

Bengali word "Kanya" means "girl" 'Shree' means beautiful, valuable, wealth, prosperity. According to Mamata Banerjee Kanyasree means "girls are our wealth" They bring in our life beauty, Prosperity. They are valuable for our life, family, society and of course for our nation. It is a scheme for the empowerment of adolescent girls (13-18).

KANYASHREE 1 (K-1):

Annual scholarship of INR 500 to unmarried girl aged 13-18 years enrolled in Grades VIII-XII or equivalent

KANYASREE 2 (K-2):

One time grant of INR 25000 to unmarried girls aged 18 years pursuing education, vocational/ technical training sports

KANYASREE 3(K-3):

Kanyasree girls' whether single or married, for, financial assistance for pursuing PG Studies under the Swami Vivekananda merit cum Means Scholarship Scheme, with a Nominal condition of at least 45% mark in Graduation and Pursuing post Graduate courses in the state of West Bengal. For pursuing Arts and Commerce, each K-3 beneficiary will receive Rs 2000/- PM and for pursuing Post Graduate studies in

science, each K-3 beneficiary will get Rs. 25001/- P.M. Alike K-1 and K-2 even the married incumbent are also eligible to enjoy the benefit

1.1 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

In Recognition of the fact the present study attempted to find out about the success rate of Kanyashree Prakalpa among girls student of North 24 Parganas district and Researcher also try Find out the impact of this Prakalpa on ongoing girls education. So researcher attempt entitle the "Study the Impact of Kanyashree Prakalpa on girl child In North 24 Parganas District The need of the study was to study the reduction of dropout of girls students, stop child marriage, empowerment of girls, helping them to continue study and achieving their goals.

1.2 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The present study was undertaken to achieve the following objectives-

- To find out the awareness of Kanyashree Prakalpa of girls student in Relation to locality
- To find out the impact of Kanyashree Prakalpa on child marriage.
- To find out the impact of Kanyashree Prakalpa on higher education.
- To find and analyse its effect on dropout of girl child.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- 1) How far the girl student of North 24 Parganas district are aware of Kanyashree Prakalpa?
- 2) What is the Impact of Kanyashree Prakalpa on the marriage of young girls in North 24 Parganas District?
- 3) How much this Kanyashree Prakalpa helping young girls in their higher studies?
- 4) How this particular Project effecting the dropout of girl children?

1.4 OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF THE TERMS:

Kanyashree Prakalpa

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❖ **IMPACT**

The action of one object coming forcibly into contact with other.

SECONDARY LEVEL

A secondary school is both on organization that provides secondary education and the building where this takes Place.... secondary schools typically follow on from primary schools and lead into vocational and tertiary education. Attendance is compulsory in most countries for students between the ages of 11 to 16.

NORTH 24 PARGANASS

North 24 Parganas is a district in Southern West Bengal of Eastern India North 24 Parganas extends in the tropical Zone from latitude 22° 11' 6" north to 23° 15' 2" north and from longitude 88° 20' east to 89° 5' east.

1.5 DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

The study is limited in North 24 Parganas District only

- > The researcher conducted the study on 5 schools in North 24 Parganas District.
- > The researcher has conducted this study only on the secondary level girl students.
- The study is limited in Government Higher Secondary schools of North 24 Parganas.

1.6 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY:

Kanyasree Project is an innovative project of Government of West Bengal. It is conditional cash transfer scheme, which is designed by the Department of Women Development of Social Welfare (DWSW) of West Bengal in August 2013, with the aim of improving the status and well-being of girl child in West Bengal by encouraging all schools teenage girls and delaying their marriage until the girl reach the age of 18 years. This scheme is introduced only in West Bengal. The main aim of this prokalpo is to increase enrolment of girls students and continue studying and to decrease dropout rate also. From this scenario I am studying over view the Kanyasree Prakalpa in North 24 Parganas District.

A literature Review shows your readers that you have an in depth grasp or your subject, and that you understand where your own research fits into and adds to an existing body or agreed knowledge.

2.2 LITERATURE REVIEW ON KANYASHREE PRAKALPA

1 Chattopadhyay and Duflo (2001) in their paper used a policy or political reservation for women adopted to study the impact or women's leadership on policy decision. They found that women were more likely to participate in policy making process if the leader of the village community was happened to be women.

2. Parashar (2004) examined how mother's empowerment in India is linked with child nutrition an immunization and suggested women to be empowered simultaneously along several different dimensions if they and their children were to be benefit across the whole spectrum of their health and survival needs

3. Karrat (2005) in her works discussed the issue of violence against women, their survival, political participation and emancipation.

4. Blumberg (2005) viewed that economic empowerment of women's capacity of decision making but also lead to reduction in corruption, armed corruption, armed conflict and violence against females in the long run.

5. Panda and Aggarwal (2005) focused on the factor like women's property status in the context or her risk of marital violence and opined that if development means expansions or human capabilities, then freedom from domestic violence should be an integral part of any exercise for evaluating developmental progress

6. The study of Khan, Etal (2006) has also explained empowerment as a process for establishing control over resource and for acquiring ability and opportunity to decision making process and its implementation.

7. Deepa Narayan (2007) made an attempt to measure women empowerment for different countries and regions for assessed points on a ten steps ladder of power and rights, where at the bottom of the ladder stood people who were completely powerless and without right and on the top stood those who had a lot of power and rights.

8. Dessai and Aggarwal Thakur (2007) in their work discussed women's political participation, legal rights and educations as tools for their empowerment.

9. Sen and Modak (2017) Revealed that while economic factors and welfare schemes in the village played a vital Role in determining the probability of a family bringing in an underage bride in the rest of India, it was not 80 in West Bengal none of the economic factor's effect the probability of a woman marriage before 18 in the state suggesting that poverty is definitely not responsible for this malaise

10. Ghosh and Dutta (2017) find that income plays a very significant role reducing adolescent dropouts among women in West Bengal. Thus a conditional cash transfer aimed at reducing child marriage would not work unless it included education as a path way. The very small transfer from the age of 13 supports, at least partially, the education cost of girls and retains them within the education system, waiting for the Big Prize' 18. This assurance of Rs 25000 discourages dropping out among the girls at the secondary level and prompts them to defer marriage till the legally permissible age

11. Karmar (2018) observed in his study that this program is very helpful in improvement of study of students, delaying Girls marriage; reduce immature mothers, mortality rate, improvement or interest or learner in sturdy etc. But inspire of this still today a large numbers of girls unable to receive education due to lack of money, so government needs to give more stress on this type of program. So that more and more girls will be benefited. But it is very appreciable effort of government of West Bengal.

12. Sumsuijaman and Haldar (2018) observed in this study that the status of child marriage has changed after the implementation of Kanyashree Prakalpa, interest in higher education has increased after the implementation of this Prakalpa. Kanyashree scheme boon for adolescent girls of West Bengal

2.3 CRITICAL OBSERVATIONS

Kanyashree Prakalpa is one of the public services initiated by the Government of West Bengal in the year 2013. Many researchers have already studied on this particular prakalpa and lots of researchers have studied on women empowerment project but I have seen a gap to study the Impact on Kanyashree Prakalpa in North 24 Parganas district.

INTRODUCTION

The success of any research work depends upon the proper methodology of the study. Since the nature of a problem is different from the nature of a problems. It is worthwhile to use the proper methodology according to the nature of the problems. The Present study is survey type research. This methodology section of the present Problem includes population, sampling Procedure tools and techniques used method used

3.1 VARIABLES

This investigation includes below mentioned variables

A. Independent variables: (Kanyashree Prakalpa) B. Dependent variables: Girl child (learner)

3.2 POPULATION AND SAMPLES

➤ The Population of this study was consisting 5 Higher Secondary School Students of North 24 Parganas District.

➤ Samples were selected through Purposive Sampling of Schools among 5 Schools all are urban Government H.S. Schools. Total 200 Samples were taken from those Higher Secondary School students.

3.3 TOOLS

For the research work, some tools are necessary to be selected for collection of data. These tools are administered in the selected schools. For this purpose the following data gathering tools had been employed.

APPLIED ON

Questionnaire

Secondary Girls Student

Interview

School Headmaster/Headmistress

3.4 DESIGN:

➤ Research Design means the exact nature of the Research Work in a systematic manner. It explains the Various Procedures, methods of data gathering and description of data gathering instruments. The design of the study gives an accurate, detailed description of how the work has been done.

➤ The Researcher has designed Qualitative analysis for the study.

3.5 PROCEDURE FOR DATA COLLECTION

By Keeping the objectives and Research Question in mind with the suitable sampling techniques, the investigator visited different Schools to collect the data with the permission of concerned authorities.

4.0 OBJECTIVE WISE ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

In the present study the Researcher analysed the collected information using various tools. The objective wise analysis and Interpretation of the data are given below.

Objective 1.

To find out the awareness of Kanyashree Prakalpa of girls student in relation to locality.

R.Q 1: [How Far the girl student of North 24 Parganas district are aware of Kanyashree Prakalpa ?]

Interpretation: The girl students of the selected Higher Secondary School of North 24 Parganas are very much aware about this Prakalpa and they are getting benefitted from this Project

Objective 2.

To find out the impact of Kanyashree Prakalpa on child marriage.

R.Q.2 [What is the Impact of Kanyashree Prakalpa on the marriage of young girls in North 24 Parganas district ?]

Interpretation:

On the basis of the information collected it is evident that Kanyashree Prakalpa has Succeeded to reduce the rate of girl child marriage of North 24 Parganas. This Project has a Positive Impact on the education of the girl Students

Objective 3.

To find out the impact of Kanyashree Prakalpa on higher education.

R.Q: 3 [How much this Prakalpa helping young girls in their higher studies?]

Interpretation: The Financial aid they receive form this Prakalpa motivates the girl students of North 24 Parganas to Continue their studies and complete their Graduation

Objective 4.

To find and analyse its effect on dropout of girl child.

R.Q.: 4 [How this Particular Project Effecting the drop out of girl student?

Interpretation: On the basis of information collected it is clear that after the Implementation of this Prakalpa, the overall dropout rate has significantly reduced from the past few years and they are continuing their education.

5.1 SUMMARY AND FINDINGS:

The girl students of the selected Higher Secondary Schools of North 24 Parganas are very much aware about this Prakalpa and they are getting benefited from this project

On the Basis of the information collected it is evident that Kanyashree Prakalpa has succeed to reduce the rate of girl child marriage of North 24 Parganas. This Project has a positive impact on the education of the girl students.

The financial aid they receive from this Kanyashree Prakalpa motivates the students of North 24 Parganas girl to continue their studies and complete their graduation.

On the basis of Information collected, it is clear that after the implementation of this Prakalpa the overall dropout rate has significantly reduced from the post few years and they are continuing their education.

5.2 Limitation

Limitation of a study is not under the control of the researcher. Limitations are factors that may have an effect on the interpretation of the findings or on the generalize ability of the results. Limitations may arise from the methodology data or method of analysis. In the present study the researcher left on stone unturned to a high standard. But owing to various reasons such as time money etc. and researcher was to carry on his research under unavoidable limitations. The limitations are as Follows:

1. This Parakalpa is implemented in the state of West Bengal only.
2. This Parakalpa is applicable only far the unmarried girl students from class VIII to graduate level only.
3. Only the Govt. School girl students can avail this benefit.

5.3 RECOMMENDATION AND SUGGESTIONS

This study indicates the needs for conducting the research on the following lines to estimate a concrete generalization.

- Studies may be conducted in different District West Bengal.
- Studies may be conducted on large number of samples.
- Studies can be conducted on Higher Secondary and Graduate levels.

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